

Automatic ABO Blood Group Classification Based On Image Processing Techniques

Md Tanvir Mahmud Prince

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
tanvirmahmudprince13@gmail.com

Abstract—In emergency situations before transfusion or donation, classifying blood group in a short time plays a vital role to save human lives. Traditionally, this is done by human technicians which involves the risk of human errors as well as sluggishness in the process. For these reasons, this paper presents a methodology using image processing techniques including thresholding and morphological operations to classify blood groups based on ABO & Rh blood typing system. The program developed in this project can be easily implemented in computational devices, i.e., Arduino, Teensy 4 etc. in order to develop a faster blood group detection system with precision and accuracy. Apart from its scope to build an automated system, it will be useful in saving precious time in determining blood group precisely thus saving peoples lives if there is no skilled person around in distant places.

Keywords—Antigen, Blood Samples, Feature Extraction, Histogram, Thresholding, Morphological Operation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Blood group determination of an individual is mandatory before delivering a blood transfusion to his/her body because it avoids the risk of injuries and blood incompatibilities. This is also necessary in the case of banking of blood from donors as well as determining compatibility between a pregnant woman and her developing fetus. Currently 36 different blood group (or type) classification systems have been recognized [1], among which ABO blood group system is the most important and the Rh blood group system is the second most important blood group system. ABO blood group classification system detects the presence of one, both, or neither of the A and B antigens on red blood cell (RBC) where as Rh blood group denotes the presence or absence of Rh(D) antigens [2]. The determination of blood type can be done in different configurations or methods such as in slide or plate [3], in tube [3], micro-plates [4], or gel centrifugation [5]. Among these methods, the micro-plates and gel centrifugation tests are more reliable but due to the requirement of heavy devices and higher cost, these two types are not commonly used. The plate test is the most popular method commonly used in hospitals, public health centers etc. Conventionally blood group determination is manually done in a laboratory by technicians who test for the agglutination of red blood cell against A, B and Rh antibodies. But there are certain emergency situations where it is necessary to hurriedly transfuse blood in patient's body in order to prevent the risk of his life and traveling to the lab to determine the blood type may not be possible. In these critical

situations, the ordinary method is to deliver the O negative blood (which is called universal donor) in patients body. However, transfusing O negative blood. is not completely out of risk. Sometimes it is possible to occur transfusion reactions due to some mismatches that could lead to the death of the patient [6]. So, the determination of the blood type before transfusion is essential even in the cases of emergency situations. Again, pre-transfusion slide/plate tests in a short time during critical situations can lead to reading error or error in interpretation of results by technicians. Since these types of human error can transform into deadly consequences, it is important to automate the procedure of these tests. Considering those points, a solution has been developed based on image processing techniques which is able to automatically detect the blood type by processing the images of slide test result. The developed system allows the processing of images captured after the procedure of the slide test and is able to detect the occurrence and nonoccurrence of agglutination and consequently determine the blood type of the patient.

II. BLOOD TYPES

Classification of blood is typically based on the presence or absence of antigenic substances on the surface of red blood cells (RBCs). This antigen can be carbohydrate, proteins, glycoside, fatty acid or some kind of lipids. Antigen is a molecule that stimulate immune system to produce antibodies inside human body. This antibodies fight against antigen. Antigen can be a virus, bacteria or fungi. Antibody binds to this antigen to inactivate them. There are many types of blood group system. But the major two types of groups are:

- 1) ABO blood group system.
- 2) Rhesus blood group system.

The ABO blood group antigens remain of prime importance in transfusion medicine. They are the most immunogenic of all the blood group antigens. This system divides blood into four group A , B , O, AB.

- 1) Group A has only antigen A in red cell and B antibodies in plasma.
- 2) Group B has only antigen B in red cell and A antibodies in plasma.

- 3) Group AB has both antigen A and B in red cell and no antibodies in plasma.
- 4) Group O has neither antigen A or B inside the red cells but both antibodies in plasma.

III. TRADITIONAL MANUAL TESTING & ITS LIMITATIONS

In order to determine the blood group of person, blood of that person is mixed with different antibody solutions. If the solution contains anti-A antibodies and the person has A antigens on red cells, then blood cell will clump together and it will be group A. If the blood does not react to any of the anti-A or anti-B antibodies which means that there is no antigen A or B on the red cells, then it will be blood group O. Similarly, Rh typing is done by mixing the blood sample with an anti-Rh serum. If the blood cells clump together in response to the anti-Rh serum, it indicates that the blood is Rh-positive. If no clumping occurs, the tested blood will be Rh-negative. Typically technicians have to perform a lot of blood group tests over a lot of samples in laboratory. When performing these above steps repetitively, there are more chances to occur human errors i.e. errors in the procedure of the tests, in reading or interpreting the results. Also the quickness in performing the test in emergency situation may lead to human error. Any one of the above mentioned errors can lead to fatal consequences for patients. So it is extremely important to automate the reading and the interpretation of the results.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A methodology based on image processing techniques is developed here in order to automatically determine the ABO and Rh type during pre-transfusion tests. The plate test method is employed here due to its low cost, availability and fast response time which is suitable for emergency situations. In this proposed system, at first three different antigens (antigen A,B & RhD) are mixed with three drops of blood in one slide. After sometime, blood may or may not react with antigens. Then the image of the tested slide is captured through camera and almost equal luminance through out whole slide is carefully maintained to obtain better result. After that the captured image is allowed to process through different image processing methods. Python 3.5 [8] and OpenCV 3.0 are used here for image processing. The flow chart of image processing techniques used for blood group classification is given in Fig. 1.

A. Separation of blood drops from sample slide

The samples were obtained from the pathological laboratory of Dhaka Medical College, Dhaka, Bangladesh and digital images of these samples were stored in JPG format. Then, each of these images were splitted into seperate images for individual identification. The first one is for testing A, second one is for testing B, third one is for testing AB and last one is for testing Rh. The original slide test image obtained from laboratory is as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Steps of determination of blood types using image processing technique.

Fig. 2: Input image of a sample slide.

B. Resizing

Sample images are of different resolutions. So, for the ease of processing, all of the images are converted to 1000x1000 pixels. This helps to get the correct ratio of blood to total image area which is used for quantification.

C. Grayscale conversion

The images are converted to grayscale as source images for thresholding operations of Otsu thresholding and adaptive thresholding (Fig. 3).

D. Thresholding

It is a convenient method for image segmentation. It is used for creating binary image from a grayscale image removing all the noises. Thresholding method replaces each pixel in an image with:

- Black pixel - if the pixel intensity $< T$
- White pixel - if the pixel intensity $> T$

Fig. 3: Separated RGB image & grayscale image

where T is a constant.

To make thresholding completely automated, it is necessary to automatically compute the threshold value T . 4 different types of agglutinins are shown in Fig. 4. In type 1 agglutinated area is smaller and there are several agglutinated areas. In type 2 these areas are larger. In type 3 there is a big area of agglutinated blood and type 4 is the least agglutinated one resulting more area.

Fig. 4: 4 types of agglutinations

Different algorithms are developed to compute threshold value automatically. Here two types of thresholding methods are used because the Otsu thresholding performs good in the first three types but doesn't show expected performance in the fourth type and adaptive mean thresholding performs good in the fourth type but doesn't show expected performance in the first three types.

1) *Otsu thresholding*: Bimodal image is an image whose histogram has two peaks. The thresholding process will be more efficient if a value approximately in the middle of those peaks can be taken as threshold value. Otsu thresholding automatically calculates a threshold value from image histogram for a bimodal image. Otsu thresholding performs good in the first three types (as in Fig. 5(a)) but doesn't show expected performance in the fourth type (as in Fig. 5(b)).

2) *Adaptive mean thresholding*: In practical condition, image has different lighting conditions in different areas. So, taking a global value as threshold value may lead to an erroneous result. For this reason, adaptive mean thresholding is used. Here, it calculates the threshold for a small region

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: Otsu thresholding of agglutinated blood sample (a) Type 3; (b) Type 4.

of the image. So different thresholds for different regions of the same image is found and it provides better results for images with varying illumination. Adaptive mean thresholding performs good in fourth type (Fig. 6(a)) but doesn't show expected performance in the first three types (Fig. 6(b)).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6: Adaptive mean thresholding of agglutinated blood sample (a) Type 4; (b) Type 3.

E. Combination operation

First thresholding operation performs good on first three types and second thresholding operation does the same on only the last type. So, these thresholded images are inverted and then each pixel value of the second one is subtracted from the first one and then again inverted. This process can successfully create binary images in which all agglutinated areas are clearly visible (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: Thresholded images

F. Contours identification

Morphological operations are performed for reshaping and reconstructing an image and also filter random noises present in the image. After morphological transformations, the contours (a curve joining all the continuous points having same color or intensity) are identified from the resulting images and these agglutinated parts are detected inside circles (Fig. 8). The contours are a useful tool for shape analysis and object detection and recognition. For better accuracy, here canny edge detection is applied before finding contours.

Fig. 8: Detected agglutinated portions of blood.

G. Quantification & result

Fig. 9: Ratio (%) of blood vs No of Samples.

At first, an image of a slide with four processed blood drops is splitted into four separated sample images. Each splitted blood drop sample image goes through an agglutination check i.e. whether that blood drop got agglutinated or not. Ratio of area with blood to the full image is measured. In the graph of Fig. 9, this ratio is plotted for agglutinated

and not agglutinated splitted blood drop samples. As all blood drops are roughly of same size, from the graph (Fig. 9), it can be clearly seen that the splitted blood samples which are agglutinated has a ratio far less than the ratio of the splitted blood drop samples which are not agglutinated. The first three types of agglutinations (early sample points of this graph) shows much smaller ratio than the fourth type (later sample points of this graph). The ROC curve obtained by varying threshold value is given in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: ROC curve.

To get the best result, the threshold value is set to 20%. If the ratio for any sample image shows value less than this threshold value, that sample is considered agglutinated. But a blood sample which gets agglutinated like type four has a ratio around 20% and even can get higher. Some not agglutinated sample images also show ratio near 20%. The only case where a not agglutinated blood drop gets detected as an agglutinated one is if the initial drop is much smaller than an average one. This can be avoided by taking precautions while processing. If a blood sample does not get agglutinated it generally has one big area containing blood. But if a blood sample gets agglutinated, blood drop generally gets splitted into several parts. In the case of fourth type, number of separated parts are high. So, for a blood drop sample having a ratio around or above 20% goes through secondary checking to calculate number of a parts that it gets separated into and if it is high then it is considered agglutinated, otherwise not. This calculation is done by finding contours and removing unnecessary smaller areas. Based on these two conditions, whether a drop of blood got agglutinated or not can be measured with 97.5% accuracy for our dataset obtained from Dhaka Medical College. The confusion matrix at the threshold value of 20% is provided below:

As each blood drop of a sample slide is used to identify a particular group(A, B, AB,O, Rh+, Rh-), analyzing each blood drop of a sample slide for agglutination and combining all of them results in determination of total blood group.

TABLE I: Performance of the Proposed Classification Algorithm.

		Actual Class	
		Agglutinated	Not Agglutinated
Predicted Class	Agglutinated	19	1
	Not Agglutinated	0	20

V. CONCLUSIONS

This proposed system uses image processing algorithm to perform blood test based on ABO & Rh blood typing system. The system can provide result within shortest possible time with precision & accuracy along with the storage of result for further use. This system will be helpful in an emergency situation when it is required to determine blood group quickly without any human error. Also, when a large number of samples are to be classified in laboratory, this automated system can help to perform the repetitive works quickly and avoiding human errors. Using the program developed in this project, a device can be constructed to detect blood group digitally. The device can be enhanced by incorporating micro-controller and camera module in it. The camera module will help to capture instantaneous images which then can be processed through the device to detect blood group successfully. Thus, the developed program can be further embedded into computational devices in order to develop a digital blood group detection device.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The paper is the outcome of a project work conducted in BUET. The authors acknowledge the cooperation and help of BUET authority. The authors also like to thank the Director of Dhaka Medical College Hospital for the permission to collect sample data from the pathological laboratory of the hospital.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. R. Storry, L. Castilho, Q. Chen, G. Daniels, G. Denomme, W. A. Flegel, C. Gassner, and M. de Haas, "International society of blood transfusion working party on red cell immunogenetics and terminology: report of the Seoul and London meetings," *ISBT Science Series*, pp. 118–122, 2016.
- [2] L. Dean, *Blood Groups and Red Cell Antigen*. National Center for Biotechnology Information (US), Bethesda (MD), Chapter 7, 2005.
- [3] M. Cressiers, "Datasheet of Diamed Diaclon Anti-A, Diaclon Anti-B, Diaclon Anti-AB," 2008.
- [4] M. Cressier, "Datasheet of Diamed-ID Micro Typing System, Card-ID. Diaclon ABO/Rh for patients," 2008.
- [5] A. Chung, P. Birch, and K. Ilagan, "A microplate system for ABO and Rh(D) blood grouping," vol. 33, pp. 384–388, 1993.
- [6] A. Ferraz and F. Soares, "A prototype for blood typing based on image processing," in *Proc. Fourth Int. Conf. Sensor Device Technologies and Applications*, IARIA, 2013.
- [7] G. Ravindran, G. Joby, M. Titus, P. Pravin, and P. Pandiyan, "Determination and classification of blood types using image processing techniques," *Int. J. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 157, pp. 12–16, Jan. 2017.
- [8] G. Rossum, "Python tutorial," Tech. Rep. CS-R9526, Centrum voor Wiskunde en Informatica (CWI), Amsterdam, May 1995.
- [9] A. M. Raid, W. M. Khedr, M. El-dosuky, and M. Aoud, "Image restoration based on morphological operations," *Int. J. Comput. Sci., Eng. Inf. Technol.*, vol. 4, pp. 9–21, 2014.

- [10] N. Srivathsa and D. Dendukuri, "Automated ABO Rh-D blood type detection using smartphone imaging for point-of-care medical diagnostics," in *IEEE Conf. Publ.*, pp. 4345–4348, 2016.
- [11] World Health Organization, "Bangladesh is still to meet the demand of safe blood supply." [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/bangladesh/news/detail/14-06-2017-bangladesh-is-still-to-meet-the-demand-of-safe-blood-supply>.
- [12] Badhan, "A voluntary blood donors' organization." [Online]. Available: <https://badhan.org/about-us>.